

Heterocyclic Compounds from β -Diketones. Part V. Sulphamido-Benzeneazodibenzoylmethanes and their Cyclisation

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Sulphamidobenzeneazodibenzoylmethanes have been obtained by the reaction of the diazotised solution of sulphanilamides with dibenzoylmethane. Their behaviours with carbonyl reagents have been studied and heterocyclic compounds such as pyrazole and isoxazole derivatives prepared.

β -Diketones readily condense with the diazonium chloride of fluoroaniline¹. It has now been observed that the diazonium chlorides of sulphanilamides also couple with dibenzoylmethane to yield sulphamidobenzeneazoketone. Thus the diazotised solution of sulphanilamide with dibenzoylmethane yield *p*-sulphamidobenzeneazodibenzoylmethane (I).

The behaviour of sulphamidobenzeneazodibenzoylmethanes towards hydrazine hydrate, semicarbazide acetate, phenyl-hydrazine, *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine acetate to yield pyrazole, pyrazole-1-amide, phenylpyrazole, sulphamyl-phenylpyrazole and isoxazole derivatives is identical with those of sulphamidobenzeneazoketones². Thus *p*-sulphamidobenzeneazodibenzoylmethane (I) yields with hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid 3,5-diphenyl-4-(*p*-sulphamidobenzeneazo) pyrazole (II); with semicarbazide acetate in ethanol 3,5-diphenyl-4-(*p*-sulphamidobenzeneazo)-pyrazole-1-amide (III) with phenylhydrazine in acetic acid 1,3,5-triphenyl-4-(*p*-sulphamidobenzeneazo)-pyrazole (IV); with *p*-sulphamylphenyl hydrazine in acetic acid, 1-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-3,5-diphenyl-4-(*p*-sulphamidobenzeneazo)-pyrazole (V) and with hydroxylamine acetate in ethanol, 3,5-diphenyl-4-(*p*-sulphamidobenzeneazo) isoxazole (VI).

(II), X = H ; (III), X = -CONH₂ ; (IV), X = Ph ; (V), X = C₆H₄SO₂NH₂ ;
 (VI) (R = N : N.C₆H₄.SO₂NH₂)

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1. A. Prakash and I. R. Gambhir, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 529.

2. Idem, *ibid.*, 1964, 41, 849.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Sulphamidobenzeneazodibenzoylmethane (I). A diazotised solution of sulphanilamide (1.8 g.) was poured on a cooled mixture of sodium acetate (65 g.), dibenzoylmethane (2.2 g.), water (10 ml.) and ethanol (50 ml.) and shaken vigorously. A pale yellow precipitate separating was recrystallised from acetic acid in 75% yield of the product (I) in golden yellow prisms, m.p. 221° (Found : S, 7.71, $C_{21}H_{17}O_4N_3S$ requires S, 7.86%). 2,4-DNP of compound (I) was obtained as red needles, m.p. 282° (Found : S, 5.32, $C_{27}H_{21}O_7N_7$ S requires S, 5.45%).

By adopting a similar procedure a few more sulphamidobenzeneazodibenzoylmethanes have been prepared and are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Substituted Sulphamidobenzeneazodibenzoylmethanes

No.	<i>p</i> -sulphamido-benzeneazodibenzoylmethane	Yield	M.P.	Colour	Mol. formula	% Sulphur		2,4 DNP M.P.
						Found	Reqd.	
1.	-Acetyl-	85%	185°	Golden yellow	$C_{23}H_{19}O_5N_3S$	7.04	7.12	236°
2.	-Thiazolyl-	85	244°	Golden yellow	$C_{24}H_{19}O_4N_4S_2$	12.93	13.06	297°
3.	-Pyridyl-	80	225°	Lemon yellow	$C_{26}H_{20}O_4N_4S$	6.49	6.61	275°
4.	-Pyrimidyl-	80	184°	Golden yellow	$C_{25}H_{19}O_4N_5S$	6.46	6.59	255°
5.	-4',6'-Dimethyl-pyrimidyl-	75	217°	Yellow	$C_{27}H_{25}O_4N_5S$	6.19	6.23	275°
6.	-Benzene-	78	168°	Golden yellow	$C_{27}H_{21}O_4N_3S$	6.48	6.62	267°
7.	-4'-Chlorobenzene-	78	168°	Pale yellow	$C_{27}H_{20}O_4N_3ClS$	6.00	6.18	269°

3,5-Diphenyl-4-(*p*-sulphamidobenzeneazo) pyrazole (II). A solution of compound (I) (4.0 g.), glacial acetic acid (15 ml.) and hydrazine hydrate (1.0 g.) were heated for 3 hours. On cooling, a yellow precipitate separating was recrystallised from ethanol in 65% yield of pyrazole (II) as yellow plates, m.p. 264° (Found : S, 7.81, $C_{21}H_{17}O_2N_5S$ requires S, 7.94%).

By adopting a similar procedure, a few 3,5-diphenyl-4-sulphamidobenzeneazopyrazoles have been prepared and are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

3,5-Diphenyl-4-(sulphamidobenzeneazo)-pyrazoles

No.*	M.P.	Yield	Formula	% Sulphur	
				Found	Reqd.
1.	257°	65%	$C_{23}H_{19}O_3N_5S$	7.12	7.19
2.	263°	65	$C_{24}H_{18}O_2N_6S_2$	13.04	13.13
3.	254°	63	$C_{26}H_{20}O_2N_6S$	6.54	6.66
4.	259°	63	$C_{25}H_{19}O_2N_7S$	6.54	6.65
5.	281°	64	$C_{27}H_{23}O_2N_7S$	6.18	6.28
6.	237°	65	$C_{27}H_{21}O_2N_6S$	6.59	6.8
7.	244°	60	$C_{27}H_{20}O_2N_6ClS$	6.10	6.23

* As recorded in Table I.

3,5-Diphenyl-4-(*p*-sulphamidobenzeneazo) pyrazole 1-amide (III). A solution of compound (I) (4.0 g.) in ethanol (20 ml.); semicarbazide hydrochloride (1.0 g.) and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were refluxed for 2 hr. The precipitate separating was recrystallised from ethanol in 60% as yellow needles, m.p. 261°. (Found : S, 7.04, $C_{22}H_{18}O_3N_6S$ requires S, 7.17%).

By adopting a similar procedure, a few 3,5-diphenyl 4-sulphamidobenzeneazopyrazole-1-amide have been prepared and are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

3,5-Diphenyl-4-(sulphamidobenzeneazo)-pyrazole-1-amides

No.*	M.P.	Yield	Formula	% Sulphur	
				Found	Reqd.
1.	249°	64%	$C_{24}H_{20}O_4N_6S$	6.47	6.55
2.	257°	64	$C_{25}H_{19}O_3N_7S_2$	12.00	12.09
3.	264°	62	$C_{27}H_{21}O_3N_7S$	6.01	6.11
4.	251°	60	$C_{26}H_{20}O_3N_6S$	6.01	6.10
5.	271°	60	$C_{28}H_{24}O_3N_6S$	5.64	5.79
6.	245°	65	$C_{28}H_{22}O_3N_6S$	6.01	6.13
7.	264°	62	$C_{28}H_{21}O_3N_6ClS$	5.63	5.75

* As recorded in Table I.

1,3,5-Triphenyl-4-(*p*-sulphamidobenzeneazo) pyrazole (IV). A solution of compound (I) (4.0 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml.) and phenyl hydrazine (1.0 g.) were heated for 2 hr. and then cooled. The solid separating was recrystallised from acetic acid in 65% yield as orange plates, m.p. 251° (Found : S, 6.60, $C_{27}H_{21}O_2N_5S$ requires S, 6.68%).

1-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-3,5-diphenylpyrazole (V) was prepared from *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine (1.9 g.) and compound (I). Recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 60% yield as red needles, m.p. 259° (Found : S, 11.34, $C_{27}H_{22}O_4N_6S_2$ requires S, 11.47%).

By a similar procedure as above, a few 1,3,5-triphenyl- and [1-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-3,5-diphenyl]-4-sulphamidobenzeneazo pyrazoles were prepared. These are recorded in Tables IV and V respectively.

TABLE IV

1,3,5-Triphenyl-4-(sulphamidobenzeneazo)-pyrazoles

No.*	M.P.	Yield	Formula	% Sulphur	
				Found	Reqd.
1.	245°	70%	$C_{29}H_{23}O_3N_5S$	6.02	6.14
2.	261°	70	$C_{30}H_{22}O_2N_6S_2$	11.30	11.39
3.	268°	68	$C_{32}H_{24}O_2N_6S$	5.63	5.75
4.	270°	65	$C_{31}H_{23}O_2N_7S$	5.63	5.74
5.	289°	65	$C_{33}H_{27}O_2N_7S$	5.39	5.47
6.	267°	70	$C_{33}H_{25}O_2N_6S$	5.62	5.76
7.	268°	68	$C_{33}H_{24}O_2N_5ClS$	5.35	5.43

* As recorded in Table I.

TABLE V

1-(*p*-*Sulphamylphenyl*)-3,5-*diphenyl*-4-(*sulphamidobenzeneazo*)-*pyrazoles*

No.*	M.P.	Yield	Formula	% Sulphur	
				Found	Reqd.
1.	257°	60%	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S ₂	10.58	10.66
2.	264°	60	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₇ S ₃	14.89	14.98
3.	267°	58	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	10.00	10.08
4.	269°	58	C ₃₁ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	9.94	10.06
5.	265°	55	C ₃₃ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	9.53	9.63
6.	234°	65	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	10.00	10.09
7.	271°	64	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₆ ClS ₂	9.49	9.57

* As recorded in Table I.

3,5-*Diphenyl*-4-(*p*-*sulphamidobenzeneazo*) *isoxazole* (VI). A solution of compound (I) (4.0 g.) in ethanol (20 ml.) hydroxylaminehydrochloride (1.0 g.) and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were refluxed for 2 hr. On adding water, a precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from acetic acid afforded 52% yield as yellow plates, m.p. 249°. (Found : S, 7.80, C₂₁H₁₆O₃N₄S requires S, 7.92%).

A few 3,5-diphenyl-4-sulphamidobenzeneazoisoxazoles were prepared similarly. These are recorded in Table VI.

TABLE VI

3,5-*Diphenyl*-4-(*sulphamidobenzeneazo*)-*isoxazoles*

No.*	M.P.	Yield	Colour	Formula	% Sulphur	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	228°	52%	Pale yellow	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ S	7.07	7.17
2.	241°	50	Pale yellow	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	13.08	13.14
3.	240°	50	Yellow	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₅ S	6.59	6.65
4.	245°	48	Lemon yellow	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₅ S	6.52	6.64
5.	268°	46	Dull yellow	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₆ S	6.14	6.27
6.	253°	50	Yellow	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄ S	6.52	6.66
7.	293°	46	Dull yellow	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₄ ClS	6.11	6.22

* As recorded in Table I.

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